

Discursive elements and Organising practices: Evidence from Conservation agriculture Tanzania

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Abstract

The main thrust of the paper is to respond to the question as to how the discursive elements and the organizing practices influence the outcomes of the training and practice of Conservation Agriculture among the cotton growers. Qualitative data has been collected from selected cotton growing villages in Tanzania in areas where there has been the Lead Farmer Initiative program. Findings show that: 1) there is poor uptake of the training in conservation agriculture; 2) Help NGO has been guided by the discursive elements of legitimation and organizational performance, with the organizing practices of legalization, clarity in philosophy and governance structure, speaking the modernizing development discourse language, and self-marketing, on the one hand, and reporting, professional staffing, and monitoring and evaluation, on the other hand. The cotton farmers have been guided by the discursive elements of economic, input, and hospitality insecurities, leading to the organizing practices of harvesting, playing safe, use of public farming inputs, welcoming the visitors and conforming to the demands of the visitors. The paper cautions that if the livelihood studies have to be viable in theorizing about strategic human agency, one of the powerful options is to take organizing practices as a double-tailed phenomenon backstopped by discourses and forward-sighted by telos.

Keywords: Discursive elements, organising practices, conservation agriculture, livelihood studies, human agency

1.0 Introductory Background

This paper aims at finding out how the livelihood discursive elements influence the outcomes of the training and practice of Conservation Agriculture among cotton growers. Conservation agriculture is what some scholars call resource-conserving agriculture. For example, Bennet and Franzel (2009:2) refer to it as focusing

on food production that makes the best use of natural goods and services without compromising their future use. To accomplish this, it uses various technologies including integrated pest management, integrated nutrient management, conservation tillage, agroforestry, aquaculture, water harvesting and livestock integration. These technologies facilitate soil replenishment using locally available organic fertilizers, cover crops and other crop rotations, and mulches; improved water management; and crop diversification to reduce the risk of crop failure from pests or unpredictable weather. Resource-conserving agriculture does not exclude the use of synthetics as long as they improve productivity without harming

The community in which the study was conducted is being served by the Help NGO, which is a charitable organization in Tanzania since 1992, aiming at enabling small and medium enterprises to carry out productive and profitable enterprises. Help got involved in an intervention to train cotton farmers in conservation agriculture through a Lead Farmer Initiative, beginning with the 2011-12 cotton season. Help NGO, as a charitable Trust, funded a Conservation Agriculture team through the Cotton Sector Development Program in order to promote uptake of conservation agriculture among cotton farmers in the regions of Mara, Mwanza, Shinyanga, and Simiyu. In the Lead Farmer Initiative, around one thousand Lead Farmers were trained in cotton agronomy and conservation agriculture techniques. The Lead Farmers received inputs to establish $\frac{1}{4}$ acre cotton demonstration plots in their villages. In the first season (2011/12), the farmers were trained in the minimum tillage by use of deep basins and herbicide applications. Deep basin tillage with its tied-ridges and diked furrows prevent runoff and improve infiltration of rain water in the soil. In the second season (2012/13), they were trained in the use of an ox-drawn 'ripper', which is a tool that looks like a small ox-plough used to break the soil; a few farmers, representative of the farmer groups, received the 'ripper' and the group members shared it. Inputs and knowledge was first delivered to Lead Farmers in the demonstration plots and they disseminated it to the farmer groups.

In May and July 2013 there was research undertaken in order to evaluate the effectiveness of the Help NGO intervention upon cotton growers. Observations were made on the application of what farmers were trained in, roles of the Lead Farmer, and functioning of Farmer Groups. Moreover, farmers' own assessment of the taught practices, adoption of the conservation agriculture techniques, and the impact outside the Farmer Groups were examined. The ultimate effects of the intervention was judged minimal. To shed more light on this disappointing outcome this paper, makes use of the same data to determine how the outcomes of such an intervention can be explained by applying the concepts of livelihoods discursive elements and organizing practices. The main thrust of the paper, therefore, becomes responding to the question as to how the livelihood discursive elements and organizing practice influence the outcomes of the training and practice of conservation agriculture among the cotton growers. As such this paper sides with the livelihood approach and tries to contribute to its understanding of local people's actions. This is an important question, as it assesses the outcome of the training towards propagation of modern agricultural technologies by TGT. The paper, therefore, becomes a critique of modernization, which is the development discourse of the day. The paper, also, underscores how the livelihood targets of the cotton farmers have impacted on the outcomes of development interventions.

After this introductory background that has put this paper in perspective, section two presents the key concepts of the paper and section three the methodological underpinnings. Section four briefly presents issues about agriculture, the NGO discourse, and Help NGO in Tanzania. Section five deals with the assessment of the conservation agriculture training experience, whose conclusion is that there has been poor uptake. A section about discursive elements and organizing practices, explanations of the poor conservation uptake, follows in section six. Section seven presents a discussion that puts in perspective the concepts of organizing practices and discursive elements with the framework of livelihood studies.

2.0 Discursive elements and organizing practices

The key concepts of this paper's analysis are discursive elements and livelihood organizing practices. I shall explain each of these concepts. A discursive element is a concept that originates from the debate on discourse. The concept of discourse can be categorized from two

basic perspectives, the structuralist and socio-political perspective. With the structuralist perspective, discourse refers to a continuous stretch of language. According to UK Essay (2013), a Latin word, "discursus" is the origin of the word "discourse". Discursus means a written or spoken communication or debate or formal discussion of debate. In language studies, however, discourse refers to language and conversations, sermons, arguments, jokes, or narrative; novels and so on. Thus, a discourse is about sentences, conversations, narratives, arguments and speeches; it is a conversation or anything said or written, a dialect and or a statement that is agreeable by the community. In this sense, a discourse is an organization of text or narration intended to describe explicit facts. With the social political perspective, discourse refers to specific ensemble of ideas, concepts and categorizations that are produced, reproduced and transformed in a particular set of practices and through which meaning is given to physical and social realities (Hajer 1995: 44). In this sense, a discourse becomes an underlying principle that motivates human beings and organizational socio-political practices. Thus, when this paper talks of discursive elements it refers to the socio-political perspective of discourses, which are strategic rationalities, that is, different intentions that become evaluative mini-discourses in a social arena (Kamanzi 2009: 8)

According to Kamanzi (2007:30), picking from Nuijten (1992:204), the concept of livelihood organizing practices refers to "patterns in the manifold and fragmented strategies of the poor that arise from particular combinations of ideas, material circumstances, and interactional potentials". Such strategies evolve around fields of power and struggle between different social actors around which certain forms of dominance, contention, and resistance may develop, and certain regularities and forms of ordering may emerge. Organising practices comprise of maneuvers, which are normally non-formal, in terms of actions as reactions, responses, and socialised behavior, with the main aim of promoting the livelihoods of the people. It is within personal networks, such as families and friendships, groups, individual alliances, ad hoc constellations, and individual relations with officials or higher placed politicians that such maneuvers take place (Nuijten 1999: np; Kamanzi 2007: 31; de Haan and Kamanzi 2011: 122). One important thing to note about organizing practices is the power issue. Organising practices happen as a result of power asymmetries. The powerless actor is often a victim of positions of the powerful actor. That is why the powerless actor will

involve in organizing practices in order to go around the powerful actor. In this paper, organizing practices are taken to be mechanisms that the main actors are involved in so as to reach their desires in a given opportunity. The argument for this paper is that organizing practices, which are responsible for the poor uptake of conservation agricultural practices, are a function and expression of discursive elements, i.e. strategic rationalities.

3.0 Methodological underpinnings

The social arena analysis in which the main actors, the farmers and Help NGO, are in constant negotiation in understanding the discursive elements. While the farmers use discursive elements to promote their livelihoods, the Help NGO uses discursive elements to promote its neo-liberal agenda. Conservation agriculture, a program implemented by Help NGO whose beneficiaries are farmers, becomes a space for concrete configurations between social actors (farmers and Help NGO personnel or their agents) who interact on something common, i.e. conservation agriculture, in what can be called a social arena according to Bierschenk and Olivier de Sardan (1997: 5-7; 26-28).

Semi-structured interviews were conducted to 35 respondents: 16 Lead Farmers, 13 members of Farmers' groups, 5 farmers non-group members, and 1 to the Ward Agricultural Executive Officer. In two villages, there were two focus group discussions of 10 members each. In total, therefore, 55 respondents were involved in the data collection exercise. There were three levels of data analysis. The first level was to assess the performance of Help NGO. The second level of analysis concerned the organizing practices that led to the performance status of conservation agriculture. The third level concerned the explanatory factors for the established organizing practices. Thus, while the first level analysis was geared towards performance assessment, the second level analysis aimed at establishing the organizing practices, and the third level analysis at unveiling the discursive elements behind the organizing practices.

4.0 Agriculture, NGO discourse and Help NGO

According to Kayandabila (2013: np), the agricultural sector in Tanzania remains the foundation of the economy. It accounts for 25% of the GDP and about 20% of traditional export earnings. It also

provides 95% of the country's food requirement and it employs 75% of the work force. Agriculture also controls inflation, since food contributes about 56% of the inflation basket and has the highest multiplier effect in the economy.

There are supportive macro and sectoral policies and programs for agriculture in Tanzania. The National Agricultural Policy of 2013 envisages the creation of a modern, commercial, highly productive and profitable agricultural sector. Tanzania's Agricultural Sector Development Strategy (ASDS) aims at achieving a sustained agricultural growth rate of 5% per annum, primarily through the transformation from subsistence to commercial agriculture. This transformation is to be private sector-led through an improved enabling environment for enhancing the productivity and profitability of agriculture. The core features of the strategy are: to strengthen public-private partnerships across all levels of the sector and to implement District Agricultural Development Plans (DADPs) as the comprehensive tool for agricultural development at district level. The sector development strategy has four priorities: to create a favourable environment for commercial activities; to improve delivery of support services with a delineation of public-private roles; to improve the functioning of output and input markets, and: to strengthen the institutional framework governing the sector.

There are a number of initiatives that have been established to promote the agricultural sector. In 2009 the *Kilimo Kwanza* (Agriculture first) initiative was launched, as a central pillar in achieving the country's Vision 2025 to become a middle-income country. *Kilimo Kwanza* aims at accelerating agricultural transformation in Tanzania, through a holistic set of policy instruments and strategic interventions towards addressing the various sectorial challenges and taking advantage of the numerous opportunities to modernize and commercialize agriculture. In 2010, the Southern Agricultural Growth Corridor of Tanzania (SAGCOT) was initiated. This is an agricultural partnership designed to improve agricultural productivity, food security and livelihoods. In 2011, the SAGCOT's Investment Blueprint was launched in order to showcase the investment opportunities in the Corridor. This Blueprint lays out a framework of institutions and activities. In 2015, the Tanzania Agriculture Development Bank was established by the government of Tanzania with the aim of assisting the government in implementing its

policies and strategies related to the agricultural sector. (Tanzania Invest: 2016)

There are two main bodies that legally identify what NGOs are: the NGO policy of 2001 and the NGO Act of 2002. According to the NGO Policy of 2001 in Tanzania,

An NGO is a voluntary grouping of individuals or organizations which is autonomous and not-for-profit; organized locally at the grassroots level, nationally and internationally for the purpose of enhancing the legitimate economic, social and/or cultural development or lobbying or advocating on issues of public interest of group of individuals or organizations (URT, Vice President's Office, 2001:10).

The NGO Act of 2002 describes NGOs as non-partisan and non-profit making; excludes trade unions, social clubs, political parties, religious organizations, and community-based organizations, even though these can establish NGOs. (URT 2002: 4).

For Farrington and Bebbington (1993:65-79), NGOs can be categorized into those that are productive-oriented and those that put emphasis on agro-ecological issues. While the production-oriented have high input approach based on the transfer of packages of technology and support systems and minding little about the local context, the agro-ecological approach promotes the use of low input technologies based on pragmatic responses to local conditions or ideological pre-dispositions to agro-ecology. According to Issa (2004:36-38), NGOs in Tanzania have played an important role between the poor, private sector and the state. They have done this through providing services that lack among the farmers, fostering grassroots institutions, linking the farmers with markets and political structures. With their flexibility, responsiveness, capability to experiment and learn from experience, linking processes to outcomes, and ability to influence commitment and participation of beneficiaries, NGOs are seen as effective alternatives to the public sector.

Traditionally, agricultural extension services in Tanzania have mostly been provided and financed by the public sector. According to Rutatora and Mattee 2001: 155), the landscape has changed because several NGOs and farmer-led initiatives have got in the scene to supplement extension service delivery of the public extension

services. Due to the government facing financial difficulties, the private sector has been left to take an increasing responsibility. With the thrust to have the extension services well-nested at the lowest level of government, as promulgated by the Regional Administration Act of 1997 and the Local Government Act No. 6 of 1999, the responsibility for implementing extension services was put with the local government authorities. This move has led to the flourishing of local-based NGOs and farmer-led initiatives to deal with agriculture.

A serious criticism is that such NGOs and farmer-led initiatives are embedded in neo-liberal thinking. According to Shivji (2007: page numbers), NGOs in Africa in general and in Tanzania in particular can only be understood from the typical aid development discourse: NGOs are forms of altruism, an incarnation of charity, enabling the wealthy to assist the people in need. According to Shivji (2007) they are a result of the imposition of the structural adjustment programmes across Africa in the 1980s and 1990s and the subsequent donations of money from the international financial institutions to NGOs to minimise poverty manifestations and hence consolidators of the neoliberal hegemony in Africa.

Shivji (2007: 53-55) outlines more criticisms of the NGOs. Most of Tanzanian NGOs are top-down organizations led by the, urban based elite. They never began as a response to the expressed need of the large majority of working people and, the relationship between them and the masses being that of benefactors and beneficiaries. NGOs are not constituency or membership based organizations. Their accountability is limited to a small group of people. Actually they are more accountable to donors than to the members, if any. Moreover, most NGOs rely almost exclusively on foreign funding, making the proverb "He who pays the piper calls the tune" hold true. In addition, the NGO-world believes in acting, and not theorizing, resulting in the lack of grand visions of society. By conflating NGOs with civil society organizations, the traditional member and class-based organizations of the working people, such as trade unions and peasant associations, are undermined.. In order to overcome such criticisms, Shivji (2007:7) argues that NGOs can be of use if they play the role of catalysts of change rather than catechists of aid and charity.

Basically, then, the NGO discourse that has been built around agriculture in Tanzania is that these NGOs are not for profit and non-partisan. Some are productive-oriented, reluctant of people's context

and some agro-ecology oriented, minding people's context; such NGOs provide services that were otherwise to be provided by the state. The NGO sector, however, is criticized as neo-liberal, top-down led by elite, limited in accountability, externally funded, lacking society's vision, and, demoter of traditional organizations.

5.0 Conservation Agriculture Training Experience

Training in conservation agriculture was done in Farmer groups through the Lead Farmers, who see their role as one of transferring to their group farmers the information they receive at the training through the establishment of the demonstration plot, calling meetings and visiting farmers to give advice. This message is very clear from the farmers interviewed: "My work is to make sure my group farmers know how to plant according to agricultural principles" (Lead Farmer Shinyanga). Originally, a group consisted of 25 to 70 members in 2011/2012 season. Members freely joined around a Lead Farmer who would pass to them the conservation agriculture techniques through the demonstration plot.

The Lead Farmers, as well as the cotton farmers, understood issues about the practice of dry season basins and the reasons behind their use. From one of the Lead Farmers there was the following admission, a discussion common to most Lead Farmers:

When you are using the basins, you reduce the need to till the whole farm; and this way, soil is not disturbed a lot and when it rains, it cannot be carried away. Instead of tilling the whole land, you just prepare the basin: this is quicker and you do not need too many people to do this. In the basins, water remains, even there is little rain and this is important for the cotton plant.

It was common to hear the issue of efficient management of manure, as can be found out from this Lead Farmer:

The use of deep basins enables the soil to retain moisture because when it rains the water does not flow as when you dig the farm by hand hoe or ox-plough. In the areas around the hole [basin] the weeds rot and act as manure to the crop and also manure is easily budgeted for, not like the local way where you just pour manure on the whole farm without measuring how much should be used for each plant" - (Lead Farmer Bariadi

Similarly, the farmers were ready to explain techniques such as planting distances and application of manure and fertilizers.

F. Have you ever gone to the demonstration plot for purposes of learning?

I. Yes

F. How many times have you been there and what happened when you were there?

I. I have gone there twice this year. I learnt how to dig terraces and to use a power tiller. I prepared terraces and used a small stick that I used to measure the 45 centimeters, as distance between a plant and another one. I used a fertilizer known as UREA after a month.

F. So, you tried to follow what you were taught, is it?

I. Yes, I understood well what the Lead farmer taught me. I slashed, tilled the land with a power tiller, planted in lines and measured the distances and sprayed poison to kill rodents. I know how to use herbicides, and even how to till and plant even without herbicides; I even know how to dress up when I am in the farm when applying poisons. ...

In short, the intended content of the training to the Lead Farmers, and eventually to the farmers, was understood. So, there was transfer of positive messages to farmers regarding conservation agriculture.

There is evidence that cotton farmers have experienced some benefits of conservation agriculture. Not only do the Lead Farmers and the trainee farmers show that they understood what conservation agriculture is, theoretically and practically. They were also convinced that it was a good thing, and have a number of positive experiences, among which higher yields and reduction in labor demands.

For sure the new technology leads to higher yields. An example is the two acres I prepared, I had forty bags [of maize] and I had never harvested this much before using this technology (Lead Farmer Magu)

In some cases, the demonstration plots succeeded in overcoming initial skepticism about the ripper:

The first time when we went to learn from his father's plot, we were shown everything. They just scratched the land with the ripper and

that was it. I thought they were not serious. In fact, even the father, after the lesson, he re-did everything and used our way of tilling the land with the plough. I am now surprised that the [demonstration] plot is nice. I shall see what to do next season. My field is one acre. I expect to get like 700 kg. He [Lead farmer] will get a little more than mine.

In general, the ripper was considered less labor demanding than basins and was the preferred method among farmers who had adopted conservation agriculture, even though it was unfortunate that less than half of the group members that were interviewed had been exposed to the ripper.

For deep basins you need more people, ploughing just needs two. The ripper requires few people, it saves time and you can do a lot in a short period (Lead farmer Bariadi). I couldn't have used basins because they take a lot of work, but for the ripper you just tie it on oxen and go easily as you prepare lines by measurements (Lead Farmer Kahama)

An assessment of the training in conservation agriculture, though, leads to a gloomy picture. As it has been seen, all Lead Farmers and farmers were well-versed in conservation agriculture techniques that they were taught. They also acknowledged the benefits of conservation agriculture practices. Of the 16 Lead Farmers who were interviewed, 12 of them planted a cotton demonstration plot in the 2011/2012 season. The numbers of demonstration plots by Lead Farmers drop in the next season. Of the 16 lead farmers trained in 2011/12, 7 attempted a demonstration cotton plot in the 2012/13 season and 9 did not. In fact, 3 of the farmers who planted demonstration plots in 2012/13 were replacement of Lead Farmers who had dropped out. This implies that, in actual fact, it was only 4 of the Lead Farmers trained in the 2011/2012 season who planted demonstration plots in 2012/13. Out of 12 Lead Farmers who planted demonstration plots in 2011/2012 season, 7 followed conservation agriculture principles. In the 2012/2013 season, 4 out of the 7 people who established the demonstration plots followed the conservation agriculture principles of digging dry basins and using rippers to till the land. However, of these 4 Lead Farmers, 3 did not begin in 2011/2012 s but in 2012/2013, implying that only 1 Lead Farmer was left of the 16 trained in 2011/2012 season. This implies that not only the uptake of planting demonstration plots is falling, but even the practicing of conservation agricultural principles by Lead Farmers.

In 2013, when the study was being conducted, Farmer Groups had generally shrunk considerably. In many cases, there were just a handful of farmers, not more than 4 members, actively involved in the groups, taking part in trainings, visiting the demonstration plots, and speaking to the Lead Farmer. Of the 13 group members interviewed, 9 had visited a demonstration plot in the 2011/2012 season, and 7 in the 2012/2013 season. Groups started well: meeting on a number of occasions for training or preparation of the demonstration plot. In the subsequent season, however, they did not have regular meetings, suggesting the waning of interest. An indication of the high proportion of group members not attending the meetings regularly could be read off the less familiarity with the ripper that was introduced in the 2012/2013 season. Only 4 of the group members had a good awareness of it, while others having little idea about it, and again others not having seen it at all. In a focus group discussion of ten farmers, where the Lead Farmer was present, none of the people present in the group discussion seemed to know what a ripper was, when asked for its usage. The Lead Farmer rushed to her house and came back to the group with a brochure to show them the ripper. By show of hands, only one person out of ten had seen it being used in someone's farm, a Lead Farmer in a close-by village.

What this account of conservation agriculture tells is that the training in conservation agriculture has not yielded positive results: dwindling uptake of demonstration plots by Lead Farmers; shrinking farmer groups, instead of growing or being maintained, and; poor uptake of conservation agriculture practices. Generally speaking, it means that the conservation agriculture programme already in its early stage has failed to perform. One might argue that it is too early to judge the performance. Much as this observation could be valid, I think that the trend shows negative performance and it is this trend that needs explanation. So, why is there poor conservation agriculture uptake, regardless of the facts that both the Lead Farmers and farmers understood what conservation agriculture is and even experienced some benefits? The next section is dedicated to exploring this question.

6.0 Discursive elements and organizing practices

This section deals with the question as to why there is poor conservation agriculture uptake, regardless of the facts that both the Lead Farmers and farmers understood what conservation agriculture

is and even experienced some benefits. The expectation would be that as farmers understood conservation agriculture and experienced some benefits, they would have tried to practice and sustain it. Instead, the experience demonstrates the opposite: the farmers seem to abandon conservation agriculture. I argue that the failure is due to organizing practices embedded in certain discursive elements. As already explained in section two, discursive elements are strategic rationalities or evaluative mini-discourses and organizing practices are mechanisms that actors engage in so as to reach their desires in a given opportunity. In this section, I present the discursive elements as foundational for the organizing practices. I group the different organizing practices according to the discursive elements in which they are embedded, i.e. by which they are informed. I shall begin with the discursive elements and the organizing practices of the TGT NGO and subsequently will present those of the cotton farmers. The elements and the practices are presented in this sequence because I argue that the farmers are primarily reacting to the NGO.

6.1 Help NGO

Help NGO is not differently characterized from the NGO discourse perspective. It is a not-for-profit and non-partisan organization: it was registered as a charitable Trust in Tanzania since 1992 under the Trustees' Incorporation Ordinance. It bears the marks of both a production and an agro-ecology orientation. In its productivity dimension, it aims at increasing cotton production and value addition, among other things. With its agro-ecology orientation, Help NGO is involved in conservation agriculture. Many of the services provided, among which the agricultural extension services, are supposed to be provided by the government. There are indicators of the elitist orientation of Help NGO: The Board of Trustees owns the NGO; the implementation of the NGO programs is done between the NGO and the Tanzania Cotton Board; the presence of the Board is a typical top-bottom approach disguised as bottom-up approach through the representation of farmers. The funding from a charitable foundation in the United Kingdom is symptomatic of its external funding.

Help NGO is characteristic of the NGO discourse. It is for this matter, its key tenet is to maintain its image of usefulness in agriculture in the cotton sector in Tanzania through realizing its vision, mission, and overall aim. The vision is "A leading catalyst for SME and farmer development in Tanzania" and the mission is "Working in

partnerships to transform youth and women SMEs and subsistence farming into global competitive enterprises". The overall aim is wealth creation through supporting creation and growth of innovative Small and Medium sized Enterprises (SMEs). For all the vision, mission, and aim, central is this question of "entrepreneurship". In order to achieve an enterprising Tanzania, Help NGO got involved in different organizing practices to make conservation agriculture work out for them best. These organizing practices can be sub-divided into two basic categories based on the discursive elements of legitimation and organizational performance. In the discursive element of legitimation, the Help NGO became involved in at least five organizing practices.

The first organizing practice was to make sure that the NGO is legal. For this matter, the NGO is legally registered as a charitable Trust in Tanzania since the year 1992, under the Trustees' Incorporation Ordinance, Cap 375. According to its legal status, Help NGO is supposed to operate in both Tanzania Mainland and in Zanzibar.

Secondly, still for legitimation purposes, the NGO has developed a clear philosophy, with an articulated vision and mission; we saw these already above. Additionally, it formulated clearly 5 core values, namely

- 1. Teamwork, partnerships and collaboration. We believe that high performing teams containing appropriate diversity can achieve what individuals alone cannot.*
- 2. Transparency and accountability. Transparency in all operations and accountability to all stakeholders (board, staff, clients, partners, government).*
- 3. Community and client involvement. In seeking solutions, we believe in harnessing and nurturing client and community based innovative ideas.*
- 4. Innovation. Success requires us to continually strive to produce breakthrough ideas that result in improved solutions to clients.*
- 5. Mentoring and leadership. We believe everyone has potential that can be unleashed for the good of the society.*

Thirdly, Help NGO has also developed a clear governance structure. It has a Board of Trustees composed of eight members, six of whom are men and two are women (having "special focus on women", as said in the mission; which by the way contradicts with this imbalance in the composition of the Board). The Board is important for legitimation. It is based on the assumption that there is representation of the people in this body: the key stakeholders, such as the farmers

and the business people are supposed to be represented in this body. An interview with one of the employees of Help NGO revealed this:

F: What is the supreme body for this NGO?

R: The Board is the supreme body for our organization. It represents all the people who have stake in this work we are doing: farmers, business people, and the donors.

F: What is its main task?

R: It has to make all the decision regarding the NGO. After it has made such decisions, then it is upon the management to implement them.

F: How many farmers are represented in this body?

R: Honestly, I do not know. But we can have people who know about farmers and they can speak for them. You do not have necessarily to have farmers. Representatives are enough. After all, in Tanzania everyone has ever been a farmer and so he/she know about farming. So, a farmer as such is not so important to be there physically. And what ideas would you like from a farmer? In front of critical people, he/she would feel very shy.

From this conversation, it is clear what kind of representation is found in such a body: these are members of the elite, i.e. those who can articulate things, and not necessarily farmers. Under the Board is the Management Team composed of a total of eleven members, seven of whom are men and four women. The gender imbalance in the Board is compensated in the Management Team, where there are 7 women and 4 men. However, the decision-making body for Help NGO is the Board.

Fourthly, for legitimation purposes, it is important to note the use of the language of the modernizing development discourse. This is a language that reverberates the key notions found in development. These are basically constitutive of the so-called development gaze, that is, broad themes which buzz around developmental (Kamanzi 2007: 11). This is a language that characterizes the NGO in its everyday appearances. Not only is this language reflected in the philosophy of the NGO, but it is also found in the key statements of the Board members. Looking at one of its recent reports, each Board member had a statement about the NGO. These were the seven statements from the Board members:

1) Diversity in inclusive SME and farmer development is a promising prospect for Help NGO (male); 2) I take pleasure in working with Help NGO to teach women to fish (male); 3) I am proud to be associated with Help NGO's contribution to the growth of Farmers and SMEs in Tanzania (female); 4) Help NGO is all about development of latent potential amongst women and youth towards uplifting the quality of their lives (male); 5) For the last twenty years Help NGO has fostered urban and rural enterprise, particularly amongst women, with great success. It stands ready to foster even stronger enterprise in the future (male); 6) I am privileged to be associated with Help NGO since 2006 in its intensive activities to alleviate poverty in the country; the far sighted projects whose implementation and completion is formally recognized by the multiple of Tanzanians at large (male); 7) Contributing to the transformation and co-creation of the Tanzanian society in pursuit of sustainable development (male), and; 7) Help NGO has done so much as a catalyst for farmer and SME development. I am truly honored to be a member of the Help NGO Family and part of its success story (female)

The underlined words (reflect big developmental ideas of entrepreneurship, progress, gender, urbanization, eradicating poverty, and sustainable development. For the sake of clarification of the modernizing development discourse, I will elaborate by way of quotes two key phenomena. The first one concerns gender and the second one sustainable development.

Interesting are the words that the women in the Board use, compared to men's words. The first woman uses the following words: "I am proud to be associated with Help NGO ..."; the second one states: "... I am truly honored to be a member of Help NGO ...". Such phrasing becomes interesting because it brings in the sense of persons belonging somewhere where they are not supposed to be as if they have not earned it. Both statements allude to "women belonging to the men's sphere". Not only do these women feel invited to the men's sphere

Fifthly, I shall present one final organizing practice for TGT that is geared towards legitimation, i.e. self-marketing. This is about creating a nice image of self-presentation to the key stakes who can then support one's presence and activities. In a conversation with one of the TGT officials, particularly on the question as to whether they are in contact with the donors of the NGO, she argued:

One of the big funders in the NGO came from Europe in 2011. He comes annually for official visits. He held several meetings, not so many because he had no time. But he managed holding meetings with the stakeholders. Of great importance are meetings he held with the Minister of Agriculture Cooperatives and Food Security; he also held a meeting with the Minister for Industry, Trade and Marketing, some key program implementing agencies, to mention but a few.

He has also visited some other big institutions in the country, institutions such as Kilimo Trust, Ford Foundation, and DANIDA. Such institutions are important to our NGO because they are potential partners because financial resources continue to be a major challenge. ...

In this quote, self-marketing is central because this big funder blows the trumpet for the Help NGO. In the second quote, however, the idea of self-marketing gets another dimension of requesting partners to come along to alleviate financial constraints.

The second set of organizing practices is related the discursive element of organizational performance. Basically, in order that the Help NGO performs well, she is engaged in the managerial control organizing practices. There could be many of them, but the ones adopted by Help NGO are the ones that were seen as appropriate, given the context of where Help NGO operates. The first mechanism concerns reporting. The Management Team has to write an annual report to the Board of Trustees. The reports talk of various issues, departing from the statement of the Chairperson of the Board to the different activities undertaken and to financial matters. The reports give a sense of accountability, not only about what the Management Team does, but also what the NGO in general does.

A second mechanism for organizational performance is professional staffing. The Management Team of Help NGO counts eleven persons. Each has got a clear demarcation for his/her duties. Some deal with managing, coordination, and administration; others deal with finance, and; again others deal with support to the different persons in the Team. Not only does such professional staffing facilitate the division of labor, but also it facilitates accountability.

Monitoring and evaluation is another mechanism. Monitoring and Evaluation is geared towards measuring the outcomes and impact of the Helping Farmers NGO's programs and towards building for future

strategies in the implementation of different activities. For monitoring purposes, there is an operational logframe to measure all activities; and a household survey to verify received data on a daily basis and to review qualitative activity-indicators. The baseline survey (2012) together with the endline survey (2015) are used to capture the impact of the Help NGO.

This section showed that Help NGO has been guided by two discursive elements, i.e. legitimation and organizational performance. It is with these two discursive elements at the background that the NGO has been involved in a number of organizing practices, such as legalization, clarity in philosophy and governance structure, speaking the modernizing development discourse language, and self-marketing, on the one hand, and reporting, professional staffing, and monitoring and evaluation, on the other hand. The two discursive elements, and the corresponding organizing practices, have as core getting to validate Help NGO as a viable NGO.

6.2 Cotton Farmers

Farmers gave meaning to conservation agriculture as an opportunity for their livelihoods through strategic rationalities or evaluative mini-discourses which we call discursive elements and in which their organizing practices vis-à-vis conservation agriculture are embedded. In the following paragraphs, three discursive elements and their organizing practices, that is, mechanisms, are discussed: economic insecurity, input insecurity, and hospitality insecurity.

Economic insecurity has been one of the discursive elements for the farmers. Cotton farmers argued that as cotton had lost economic value, they could not risk putting much effort in growing cotton, which they cannot eat, and which even if sold could not raise enough money to buy food. Similarly, they could not afford buying fertilizers and herbicides at the expense of taking care of prime livelihood needs, such as taking care of the sick and provision of education for their children.

Regardless of the conviction and proof that with the use of herbicides, there was more yield as the insects that attack cotton are killed, Lead Farmers did not want to invest their own money in herbicides for their plots. Even in cases where the Lead Farmer explained the potential benefits of herbicides and has extended conservation agriculture

beyond the demonstration plot, there was unwillingness to commit extra resources to herbicides: “Yes, application of herbicides leads to more yields; but assume I am to plant more than one acre - how much money will I need?” (Lead Farmer Bariadi)

The most commonly cited reason for not practicing the new techniques was lack of cash to buy inputs, especially herbicides.

LF: I did not use dry season basins in my own field because at that time I did not have cash to buy herbicides (Lead Farmer Kahama)

LF: By the time I was preparing my own plot, money was spent buying food for the family; I could not have purchased agricultural inputs (Lead Farmer Shinyanga)

Due to economic insecurity, both the farmers and Lead Farmers engaged in “harvesting” to address the insecurity. Farmers thought of Help NGO as a source of finance and strategized differently in order to “harvest” the moneys. The formation of farmer groups was for harvesting purposes: it was close relatives who composed the groups so that whatever accrued from Help NGO would be appropriated by people related by kin. One of the farmers argues that he knew all the group members because they were related:

That one there coming is a group member. ... Yes, he is my uncle. Many of my group members are my relatives. And there is no way I cannot know my relative in this village. ... You see, with relatives it is easy to work together and whatever is obtained gets to relatives. If you are not, you will always quarrel over nothing. Do you see this plot we are in now that we use for demonstration, it was given for the group by my father.

A farmer argued:

I thought that my brother who is the Lead Farmer in this village would remember me. But he eats the money alone and he does not want even to give us the ripper. He goes to Mwanza, and I know he gets something, but my friend you will never even receive a bottle of beer from him. I supported him to become the Lead Farmer here in this village after being asked by the agricultural officer. I thought he would remember me.

Cross-checking this information regarding groups of people related by kinship with one of the TGT representatives, he argued:

The ethnic people here have very big families. They work together, eat and drink together also. Even when opportunities come, they share them as a family. They know each other, love one another, and hide so many things together. Actually, if I am to be honest, I did not see it as a problem having these people together to form groups. For me it was easy to do it that way than bringing together people who are not related.

Thus, the formation of groups functioned as an avenue for harvesting for wealth sharing among family members, on the one hand, and on the other hand it was allowed to happen in order to avoid wastage of time and to manage conflict.

Some farmers had joined the farmers' groups thinking that there were lots of money that they would harvest very fast in order to pay their debts with microfinance institutions. When they discovered that this was not possible, they were afraid that they would have problems if they continued participating in the farmer groups. In Bariadi, for example, there were concerns about defaulting in relation to farmer groups, which were previously involved in contract farming arrangements. These farmers defaulted on their contract farming loans following the fall in cotton price. The farmers, therefore, became nervous to attend group meetings thinking that they would be challenged over their debts. They thought also that if they got money later, they would be forced to pay off their debts as they would be known as members of the new groups. Worse still, they thought that police would come for them the moment they would be in group meetings.

Due to the economic insecurity, the Lead Farmers too engaged in "harvesting". The Lead Farmers see Help NGO as a special money-spinner and they would make sure that they benefit from it as much as they can. One Lead Farmer vowed to defend his position:

I do not get a lot from this work; it is voluntary. But now and then we go to Mwanza and they pay us something. This is not small at all and it keeps me living. I shall defend it, come what may.

In one of the groups in Bariadi, a very big conflict occurred. Farmers in the group demanded that the Lead Farmer would be removed from his position. The Lead Farmer had this to say about the conflict:

I understand them. Some people do not want me in this position. They wish they were the ones here. They think we get a lot and we

have a lot of influence in the village because of being connected to Help NGO Mwanza. I do not care; I cannot agree that they remove me easily from this position. I shall fight to death. I shall show them that I am a man. My friend, I cannot easily agree that they remove from me this shoe; I cannot walk with a sock or bare feet! The little, actually big compared to what many people get here, is important for me.

And another Lead Farmer argued:

I understand that it is service we are doing. But they need to give us more money. In the next meeting in Mwanza I shall say it even if I think that the guys shall not be very happy. But they have to give us more money. Where shall we eat from, police? No way. It is in Help NGO that we have to eat from.

Much as the claim from the Lead Farmers is that they were gaining little from their position, they still needed to defend their position as Lead Farmers. With the ongoing mistrust, they were losing legitimacy. And if they did not defend themselves, therefore, there was possibility that they are removed from their positions. An atmosphere of mistrust was created between Lead Farmers and cotton farmers. The latter are of the opinion that Lead farmers earn a lot from their service and the former refute this:

You see, it is hard for people here in the village to believe and trust you. When you go for training they think that you are given much that you do not share with them; especially they think that you are given money. They think that we are paid a lot and we do not tell them; they think we benefit a lot, while the truth is that there is little, if anything that we do gain. This is actually work for free if you look at the time you use and the risks you undergo (Lead Farmer Magu)

This Lead Farmer is on the defensive because he has lost trust and credibility from the farmers. It is true that he gets some financial benefits from Help NGO; this is something he does not want to admit; that is why he ends up with this maneuver of self-justification.

The selection of the Lead Farmers took into consideration the needs of the Ward Agricultural Officer (WAO), who would benefit from the little allowances that the Lead Farmer got from Help NGO. In principle, it is supposed to be the farmers selecting their own Lead Farmers. However, from one of the conversations with a farmer, it became clear that it were not villagers as such who selected the Lead Farmers.

F: How often do you visit your Lead farmer?

R: Not so often.

F: Why?

R: I do not have lots of things to do with him. Besides, I have never liked him.

F: Why don't you like him and you selected him among many to become your Leader in farming?

R: That I selected him is not true. He and others are friends to our agricultural officer. The agricultural officer told us to elect this one because he said that he knew him very well because they worked together for a long time and he knew that he was going to assist us. We know that it is this way it works because at the end of the day they eat together.

F: Eat together?

R: Yes, they share whatever comes from Help NGO. So, we say that we want the Lead Farmer, but in fact he is wanted by the agricultural officer.

In this conversation, it is clear that the agricultural officer is strategic in the choice of the Lead Farmer. He has to make sure that whoever gets in is loyal to him so that they can share with him whatever the benefits are obtained from Help NGO. In a ward, the Lead Farmer is strategically placed to serve, among other actors, the agricultural officer.

Input insecurity is another discursive element. Help NGO was expected to provide inputs for the farmers. In Maswa, both Lead Farmers and group members expressed frustration at the difficulty of putting their training into practice in the absence of herbicides:

At the beginning, he [Lead Farmer] used to visit us but these days it is a long time since he has visited me. For me, I think even if he visited we would end up discussing what I cannot put into practice; so you end up seeing his visit as a waste of time because he does not come with anything and he just talks and talks without showing you anything (Group Farmer). As I have told you, how can they practice when they have no farm inputs needed? They learn and if you meet them they will give you answers on how to do conservation agriculture, but no one has practiced it (Lead Farmer Maswa)

Lead Farmers, even though they did not say this directly to Help NGO agents, believed that the farm implements they received were supposed to come from the government through Help NGO. And since these implements were from the government, they were supposed to be for free. The farmers themselves thought that these implements were actually theirs, freely provided by the government, which unfortunately had ended up in the hands of the Lead Farmers.

When I joined the group, I thought that we were going to get farm inputs and we would pay later. In fact, there is no reason for paying back what we had got from the previous contract farming people. We are poor people and government is supposed to give us inputs. And these groups are a place for government to do this.

The thinking is that the government was supposed to provide such services to the farmers. This happened in the past with the agricultural cooperatives. The provision of such implements for the Lead Farmers was a sign that the government had come back to meet its farmers, as it used to be with the cooperatives. To the farmers' disappointment, this was not the case.

There are Lead Farmers who did not plant demonstration plots in 2012/13 because they could not access Maksai (i.e. a trained bull to pull the ox-plough or ripper) or they did not have the correct yoke for the ripper. Basically, these were not among the assets they had, implying that they were to borrow or hire them, both would come at a cost. More so, in some areas, for example Bariadi, it was even claimed that the cattle were too weak in the dry season to pull the ripper. As technology is concerned, there were complaints about the use of dry season basins. They demanded more labor, which was already compromised by sickness, on the one hand, and could not be paid for as there were already economic deficits, on the other hand.

The use of dry season basins is difficult when digging the holes and it is costly because you have to hire people to plant (Group member Magu). Others see the procedures followed in measuring and digging as complicated and think ploughing by ox is easier because they plough and plant at the same time. This saves time than if they have to start measuring (Lead Farmer Magu). More people are needed in dry deep basins because two people are needed to hold the rope and another person to plant. ... In deep basin farming you have to adhere to measurements. This makes it more labor demanding (Lead Farmer Bariadi)

One of the organizing practices stemming from this discursive element of input insecurity is “playing safe”, as can be observed from the following. A Lead farmer, who was not sure about the continuity of the benefits of conservation agriculture did not think it was a wise idea to change the land management practices outside the demonstration plot.

I: Did you use the ripper and other methods you have learnt in the other plots?

LF: No, I did not because I think that these practices are to be used only in the demonstration plot. I understand that if I use basins, the ripper, and herbicides, I can get a lot of cotton, I have seen in the past season. But, for how long can this last, forever? And if anything went wrong, how would I gain back my already lost plot to these new practices? ... For me, that is why I think that even in this season, I cannot go beyond my plot. And still, you cannot always rely on what you are sure you cannot have always, for example, the ripper and the herbicides.

I: And why did you not try these methods in the maize plot?

LF: If these methods were brought for cotton, why should I try them with other crops? For example, I cannot risk with maize. You see, maize is our only food here. Suppose, I tried to use these herbicides and all my maize died, would that not mean death for me and my family? So, you can see why trying some of these new things can be a problem. It is better that you continue with what you know and you get little, but not over-want things and you lose everything.

Misuse of public farming inputs was another organizing practice informed by this discursive element of input insecurity. For example, there are cases in which Lead Farmers were replaced for failing to carry out their duties whilst keeping inputs for their own private use. In two cases [Magu, Bariadi] where the Lead Farmers were using the ripper in their own fields, the group members claimed to have no knowledge of conservation agriculture. These Lead Farmers used all the inputs they were given, and nothing went to the demonstration plot for other members of the group to benefit.

Hospitality insecurity is the third discursive element. Hospitality refers to a generous or friendly way of receiving someone, particularly a guest or friend or visitor. In so many African cultures this seems to be a value that each one is expected to have and show to visitors. From this perspective, help NGO was seen as visitor or guest who was

supposed to receive a hospitable welcome. A farmer in Magu expressed his views when he was asked why he joined the farmer group, and left after a couple of months:

F: For how long did you remain as group member?

I: For three months

F: Why that short?

I: When you see a visitor coming, you have an obligation to welcome him. Visitors bring blessings, even the Bible tell us this. You will talk with your visitor. He will tell you what he has; you will tell him what you have. And you can see if the visitor is a blessing to you or not or he also wants you to be his blessing.

From this conversation, not only is there a welcome as an obligation, but also there is always something expected from a visitor, especially blessings. So, it is welcoming, but with a motive of getting something out of the visitor. Thus, this farmer joined expecting that cotton price issues would be addressed, for instance, though this was not the case.

Conformism was another organizing practice to express the hospitality insecurity. This organizing practice is about accepting to do something because it is a condition, even if you are not convinced of it. With this organizing practice, the farmers' accepted to form farmer groups in order to receive the training; this was a prerequisite from Help NGO. Their acceptance was like welcoming a visitor, who could, then, be turned into an opportunity to address vulnerabilities.

So, your visitor comes. You know he has something to offer to you. And he tells you form groups so that I can work with you. Can you refuse? If you refuse, you should be mad. And if you refused and there is really something nice, what do you gain?

So, welcome the visitor; do what he wants, if he promises that you will be assisted from that. If he does not get to his promises, then leave him alone. After all, you were not born with him. ...

One of the biggest reasons for the massive shrinkage of membership was the fact that it was clear to members that Help NGO was not going to benefit everybody, as the NGO seemed to many farmers:

Help NGO came as visitor to promote we the farmers and this was a good thing, at least judging from what they told us. But I immediately

discovered that it was interested in us growing growing growing growing, but not providing us with anything. The Lead Farmers were the only one benefiting. I discovered that Help NGO was a blessing to some people, and not a blessing to most of us in need. For example, Help NGO never indicated that they would have propagated for higher cotton prices. Now, what was it for?

More particularly, some other farmers argued that it was neither going to supply money nor organize loans:

You see here in the village, when people hear of something coming from outside they think there is money coming, and once they find it is not coming or it is another form of assistance and not money, obviously they will run from the group (Group Farmer Kahama)

For loan organization and marketing cotton, this conversation in a focus group discussion in Kahama is seminal:

I. When you joined the group, what did you expect?

GF 1: I thought I would know a lot about how to grow cotton.

GF 2: For me, I knew that we were organized in such groups so that we can get loans in order to buy farm implements and return the money later after harvesting.

GF 3: I thought that these people after teaching us how to grow cotton, giving us loans, they would also provide the market for our cotton. Instead, already in these groups, the prices of cotton fell down. Now, what were the groups for? I stopped attending the meetings as I went into growing rice and groundnuts. I could eat rice, and sell it. The same to groundnuts.

So, with the hospitality insecurity, the farmers were “compelled” by their value system to welcome the visitor and conform to conditions of the visitor, Help NGO, expecting to have their needs addressed. They expected to have more resources in cotton farming so that what they already had would continue assisting them in their already existing needs. Help NGO resources would add to theirs, and they would generate more economic resources. It is in this way that the farmers saw themselves growing. With the disappointment in expectations, their zeal to deal with visitor died.

This section showed that the farmers have been guided by three discursive elements of economic, input, and hospitality insecurities. With these three discursive elements, the farmers and lead farmers

were involved in such organizing practices as harvesting, playing safe, use of public farming inputs, welcoming the visitors and conforming to the demands of the visitors. The three discursive elements, and the corresponding organizing practices, have as core maximizing the use of the Help NGO.

7.0 Discursive elements, organising practices, and livelihood studies

The thrust of the paper was to respond to the question of how the discursive and organizing practices influence the outcomes of the training and practice of Conservation Agriculture among the cotton growers. The poor uptake of the training in conservation agriculture is a function of organizing practices, which are also a function of discursive elements. Organizing practices, however, are also for a purpose. For this matter, organizing practices become a double tailed analytical concept with the discourse phenomenon at the back and the teleological aspect in front. Thus, if livelihoods studies have to become relevant in the analysis of people's lives, they have to take seriously people's strategic agency as determined by their discourses and their telos.

The concept of discursive elements calls for the attention to discourses. This is because at the core of the discursive elements are rationales to guide the thinking and practice. From this perspective, for the future of livelihood studies it is important that discourses are taken into consideration because human agency is guided by discourses. Organizing practices are the expression of human agency and discursive elements the underlying structures, which are basically discourses.

What the previous section has described is the link between discursive elements and organizing practices: that organizing practices are informed by discursive elements. This has been presented from the experience of the two main actors in the conservation agriculture arena, cotton farmers and the Help NGO. This section offers a reflection about the relationship between discursive elements, organizing practices, and the livelihood approach, particularly the livelihood strategies. From the perspective of the livelihood studies, the paper suggests that organizing practices are also livelihood strategies, with the only difference with other

livelihood strategies that organizing practices put more emphasis on power relations. I show, then, that the other livelihood strategies we have known about in the livelihood literature, basically, put emphasis on some other aspects of people's livelihoods.

Generally speaking, livelihood strategies, according to Chambers and Conway (1991: 10-11) and de Haan (2000: 5-10) are responses to adequately satisfy people's basic needs and to secure them against shocks and stresses. In their temporal dimension, when they are short-term, they take the shape of coping strategies, and when they are long-term, they take the nature of adaptive strategies. This understanding of livelihood strategies is based on temporality.

De Bruin and van Dijk (2003:11) add on this issue of strategizing the dimension of the assessment process, and see strategic actions as pathways, which actually arise

out of an iterative process in a step-by-step procedure in which goals, preferences, resources and means are constantly reassessed in view of new unstable conditions ... Individuals decide on the basis of a wide range of past experiences, rather than on a vision of the future, while these recollections of the past depend to a great extent on our intellectual concern in the present. Knowledge ... is gathered in an incremental learning process.

From the assessment of past experiences, people are able to learn from how they dealt with the past (discarding the future) in order to see how to deal with the present. In this way knowledge is built, and rather than strategic behavior being out of spontaneity, it is out of assessment of the past.

To this dimension of the assessment process of the past, de Haan and Zoomers (2005: 43), looking at pathways, underlines the coordination process, on the one hand, and strategic behavior being embedded in history (as it is for De Bruin and van Dijk), and in social differentiation and institutional processes (different from De Bruin and van Dijk), on the other hand:

patterns of livelihood activities which arise from a coordination process among actors. This co-ordination arises from individual strategic behaviour embedded both in a historical repertoire and in social differentiation, including power relations, and institutional processes, which both pre-structure subsequent decision-making.

De Haan and Zoomers (2005: 43) differentiates between observed regularities or patterns in livelihood among particular social groups (pathways) and the individual actor's life paths (trajectories).

Kamanzi (2007:31; 2012:21), brings in the understanding of livelihood strategies from the perspective of organizing practices. The emphasis is on the origin of livelihood strategies from the perspective of power (one of the elements in de Haan and Zoomer's analysis of the origin of strategies, expressed as pathways – just seen above). For Kamanzi (2007:31; 2012:21), organizing practices are

non-formalised forms of manoeuvres in terms of actions as reactions, responses, and socialised behaviour geared towards livelihoods promotion, particularly when relationships are regulated by power asymmetries.

In Kamanzi (2007), the argument is that the farmers who are beneficiaries of Dutch aid through the rural development programs engage in organizing practices as maneuvers or manipulations to appropriate what the powerful donors, the Dutch development partners, bring to the programs from a gender perspective, Kamanzi (2012) shows how women, who are less powerful compared to men, appropriate resources that accrue from fishing which are mainly in the hands of men.

In this paper, the Help NGO engages in organizing practices in order to adhere to the NGO discourse, that is, proving itself as a viable charitable institution able to bring about modern development in the agricultural sector. The farmers, who are beneficiaries of Help NGO, engage themselves in organizing practices to appropriate what the NGO comes along with in terms of finances and agricultural inputs, with the expectation of alleviating their vulnerabilities. Chambers (1989: 1-7) sees individual vulnerability and household vulnerability as caused by external dynamics of risks, shocks, and stress, on the one hand, and internal dynamics of defenselessness, on the other hand. While the external dynamics refer to insecurity and exposure, the internal dynamics refer to a lack of means to cope with damaging loss. De Haan (2012:349) sees shocks, trends, and seasonal variations as types of vulnerabilities. In this paper, for both the NGO and the farmers, expectations are very crucial; they carry the teleological aspect of organizing practices. While for the NGO, it is about surviving as a viable charitable institution, for the farmers, it is about livelihood promotion. In livelihood studies, expectations correspond with

livelihood outcomes, including all of what people actually achieve from their livelihoods (actual outcomes) and aspire to achieve in the future (potential outcomes – livelihood goals).

However, it has to be noted that both the NGO and the farmers engage in organizing practices while relating to each other. This implies that both interactors perceive the other as being powerful. For example, the power of the NGO with regard to the farmers lied in being perceived as having financial and material resources. On the other hand, the NGO feels the power of the farmers in terms of their capacity to de-legitimize the NGO, that is if it does not meet the expectations as a registered NGO.

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